

Reveduti, Correcti, Aprobati et Confirmati: The Digital Edition of the Statutes of Ascoli

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ABSTRACT (ENGLISH)

This paper presents the digital edition of the statutes of Ascoli, a normative corpus promulgated in 1377 and preserved in a printed edition of 1496. The project aims to make a significant source for the legal and institutional history of the city accessible through a digital edition, based on a full transcription encoded in XML according to the TEI guidelines. The edition highlights the structural complexity of the statutory text by making explicit references to people, places, events, and thematic domains, and provides differentiated modes of access for both specialist and non-specialist audiences. Particular attention is devoted to the sustainability and long-term preservation of the project by adopting a static architecture. Finally, an experiment in automated named entity recognition shows that large language models locate entity-bearing regions with reasonable accuracy, while span delimitation remains challenging, reflecting the complexity of the source's vernacular register.

Keywords: digital scholarly edition; communal statutes; named entity recognition

ABSTRACT (ITALIANO)

Reveduti, Correcti, Aprobati et Confirmati: l'Edizione Digitale degli Statuti di Ascoli

Il contributo presenta l'edizione digitale degli statuti di Ascoli, un corpus normativo promulgato nel 1377 e conservato in un'edizione a stampa del 1496. Il progetto mira a rendere accessibile una fonte significativa per la storia giuridica e istituzionale della città attraverso un'edizione digitale, basata su una trascrizione codificata in XML secondo le linee guida TEI. L'edizione valorizza la complessità strutturale del testo statutario rendendo espliciti i riferimenti a persone, luoghi, eventi e ambiti tematici, e offre percorsi di consultazione differenziati per pubblici specialistici e non specialistici. Particolare attenzione è dedicata alla sostenibilità e alla durata nel tempo del progetto, attraverso l'adozione di un'architettura statica. Infine, un esperimento di riconoscimento automatico di *named entities* dimostra che i *large language models* individuano le regioni contenenti entità con una discreta accuratezza, mentre la delimitazione precisa degli intervalli rimane complessa, riflettendo la complessità del registro vernacolare della fonte.

Parole chiave: edizione digitale; statuti comunali; named entity recognition

1. INTRODUCTION

Communal statutes represented one of the main forms of normative production at the local level and constituted the foundation of the urban legal order in communal Italy during the medieval period. The statutes should be understood as dynamic instruments, capable of translating into legal form political balances, institutional structures, and social practices in continuous transformation (Meccarelli, 1999). These codifications regulate a wide range of domains: from civil and criminal law to the organisation of the local government, from urban space management to the regulation of economic activities and social practices, thus offering an integrated vision of the city.

The statutes of Ascoli (modern-day Ascoli Piceno) emerge as a significant example in central Italy. As emphasised by Zdekauer and Sella, these statutes complete the series of statutory codifications of the major communes located along the main Italian trade routes (Zdekauer & Sella, 1910: 10). This chronological sequence includes Siena in 1310, Florence in 1325, Perugia in 1342, and Ascoli in 1377. *Statuti del Comune e del Popolo di Ascoli* were compiled and promulgated in 1377 by a group of local jurists, judges, and legal experts, tasked with reviewing and updating the existing normative corpus (De Santis, 1988: 199–205). This legal code remained the main regulatory reference for the city throughout the 15th century, and, in 1496, was translated from Latin into the vernacular and published in print; this edition now forms the textual basis for the digital edition.¹

The Ascoli corpus allows us to analyse the functioning of the communal statute both as a normative instrument and as a historical source, as well as to experiment, through a digital edition, with new analysis

¹ The digital edition can be consulted at: <https://statutiascoli.it/>. The project material is available in the GitHub repository: <https://github.com/statutiascoli/statutiascoli.github.io>.

methods and to enhance a significant statutory collection of the communal age. The project for a digital edition of the statutes of Ascoli responds to the need to improve access to a text of major relevance to the city's legal and institutional history, whose specialised language and articulated structure have traditionally limited its readership to specialists. As occurred in 1496 with the translation into the vernacular and the printing of the statutes, this digital edition aims to enhance the statutory text through contemporary technologies. From this perspective, the project was guided by a set of key research questions:

- How can the hierarchical and cross-referential structure of a statutory corpus be represented in TEI to support non-linear navigation?
- How can semantic modelling through named entities and thematic categories transform a legal text into a network of meaningful, explorable resources?
- How can the structural and semantic modelling of the statutes be translated into an interface that supports both specialist research and public-oriented exploration?

These questions guided both the editorial choices as well as the design of the interface and consultation tools. The digital edition that emerged from this process is based on a transcription encoded according to the XML-TEI standard, on the semantic modelling of people, places, events, and thematic domains, and the development of mediation tools alternative to linear reading. From this perspective, the digital edition is not conceived merely as a transcription of the source, but as a scholarly infrastructure that supports multiple levels of access and interpretation for different audiences.

2. STATE OF THE ART

Long before the emergence of digital scholarly editions, medieval communal statutes had attracted the attention of historians, expressed through practices of collection, cataloguing, and preservation. A significant example is *Catalogo della raccolta di statuti, consuetudini, leggi, decreti, ordini e privilegi dei comuni, delle associazioni e degli enti locali italiani dal Medioevo alla fine del secolo XVIII* preserved at *Biblioteca del Senato della Repubblica "Giovanni Spadolini"*, which documents a wide corpus of statutory sources. Access to the catalogue has been extended through the digital facsimile of 150 statutes, including the statutes of Ascoli.² While not constituting digital editions in a strict sense, these resources provided an essential foundation for later developments in the field.

Building on this long-standing scholarly and institutional interest, since the early 2000s, Digital Humanities have devoted increasing attention to enhancing medieval normative sources through new editorial models, especially digital editions. In the Italian context, where communal laws constitute a core body of medieval normative production, projects such as *Statuto comunale di Bologna del 1376*, *Codice Diplomatico della Lombardia Medievale*, and the digital edition of *Statuto di Vicenza del 1264* represented some of the first research experiences in this historical field to employ XML-TEI encoding to make normative documents available in digital form (Zorzi, 2007; Siciliano & Salardi, 2009). These initiatives laid the foundations for the development of shared methodologies for the encoding and publication of statutory texts. They thereby contributed to the establishment of XML-TEI as the reference standard for the structured representation of texts and their semantic entities.

Within this evolving landscape, the field of digital editions of medieval sources was further enriched by projects that combined philological and editorial rigour with an increasing attention to issues of accessibility and audience. The diffusion of Edition Visualization Technology (EVT, Rosselli Del Turco, 2019) played a crucial role by providing a stable and widely adopted environment for the online publication of digital scholarly editions, facilitating their circulation beyond a strictly specialist domain.³ Within this framework, projects such as *Codice Pelavicino* and *Statuti di Monterosso* represented significant attempts to address a broader public, particularly at the local level. *Codice Pelavicino* employed the EVT to facilitate access for users interested in local history, offering multiple points of access to the text through images, indexes, full-text search, and structured lists of named entities (including places, people, roles, coins, and notable terms). The digital edition of *Statuti di Monterosso* followed the same model, further extending it through the integration of an Italian translation displayed alongside the transcription and the facsimile (Salvatori et al., 2017; Salvatori, 2022).

² The catalogue currently comprises 790 manuscripts dating from the XIII to the XIX century, 43 incunabula, and more than 4,000 printed editions produced between the XVI and the XX century. The catalogue is available at: <https://www.senato.it/w3/Biblioteca/catalogoDegliStatutiMedievali.nsf/home?OpenPage>. The digital reproduction of the 150 statutes is available at: <https://www.senato.it/w3/Biblioteca/StatutiMedievali.nsf/home?OpenPage>.

³ The EVT software is open source. It is available at: <http://evt.labcd.unipi.it/>.

While these projects demonstrate how EVT can support diversified modes of access and improve the usability of scholarly editions for non-specialist audiences, the overall interaction model remains largely text-centred. In particular, tools for extratextual and spatial navigation, such as maps or timelines, are not natively integrated into the EVT environment. This limitation is especially relevant for editions of sources related to urban history, where spatial visualisations can play a crucial role in connecting documentary content to the historical geography of the city, fostering a more immediate and intuitive form of engagement.

The need for integrated extratextual tools can be understood as part of a shift in the theory of digital editing, where increasing attention has been paid to the audience. Recent scholarship has challenged the idea that critical editions are intended exclusively for specialist users, emphasising how digital publishing radically transforms access and potentially broadens the audience to include students, local history experts, and citizens interested in cultural heritage (Salvatori, 2022; Hajo, 2025). In this perspective, tools such as maps, indexes, and exploratory paths assume a central role, supporting diverse users and use cases through forms of guided consultation, while also fostering dynamics of discovery and serendipity (Barabucci et al., 2017; Chapman et al., 2025). In this sense, guided paths foster self-learning by encouraging users to explore the collection on their own (Salvatori, 2022: 235).

Alongside the redefinition of audience, a further critical dimension of digital editions concerns the sustainability and longevity of digital projects. Analyses on the life cycle of DH initiatives have shown that a significant percentage of projects become inaccessible within a few years, often due to technological obsolescence or the cessation of infrastructural support (Andreose et al., 2025). These critical issues have contributed to focusing attention on design strategies oriented towards persistence and infrastructural simplicity.

3. THE DIGITAL EDITION

The digital edition of the statutes of Ascoli was conceived as a tool for broad and differentiated use. It aims to transform the statutory text into digital form while providing a system that supports multiple modes of exploration and consultation, tailored to both specialist audiences and non-expert users.

The transcription is based on the critical edition of *Statuti di Ascoli Piceno dell'anno MCCCLXXVII* (Zdekauer & Sella, 1910).⁴ The text of the 1910 edition was initially processed through OCR techniques and subsequently revised and corrected manually, with systematic reference to the 1496 incunabulum preserved at the Biblioteca del Senato della Repubblica, which constitutes the textual basis of the digital edition.⁵ The final transcription was then encoded in XML in accordance with the guidelines of the Text Encoding Initiative (TEI).⁶ The structure of the edition reflects the organisation of the 1496 printed text and is divided into two main volumes, *Statuti del Comune* and *Statuti del Popolo*, each subdivided into books and rubrics. Figure 1 offers an overview of the internal organisation of the statutes, illustrating both the hierarchical structure of the corpus and the thematic orientation of each book.

In total, the corpus comprises 513 rubrics, which constitute the fundamental textual units of the edition. Each rubric is encoded as an autonomous unit, identified by a sequential number, a title, and the full normative text. Alongside the textual structure, the XML-TEI file integrates structured lists of named entities for people, places, and events, defined in the *teiHeader* and annotated throughout the document. These lists comprise 28 individuals, 126 places, and 68 festivities or events, forming the semantic backbone of the edition and providing the basis for alternative modes of access to the statutory text. The hierarchical structure encoded in the XML file is reflected in the online representation of the text, which allows navigation by volume, book, and rubric. Each rubric is accompanied by digital images of the 1496 incunabulum alongside its transcription.⁷ This choice maintains a clear link to the original source and ensures editorial transparency by enabling direct comparison between the transcription and the printed text.

⁴ Although the statutes were originally promulgated in 1377 in Latin, the original version is no longer extant. The only complete version of the statutes transmitted to us is the vernacular edition printed in 1496. The critical edition edited by Zdekauer and Sella, used as the reference for this digital edition, reproduces the 1496 incunabulum held at the Biblioteca del Senato della Repubblica "Giovanni Spadolini".

⁵ OCR processing was performed using Tesseract OCR: <https://github.com/tesseract-ocr/tesseract>.

⁶ The TEI P5 Guidelines are available at: <https://tei-c.org/guidelines/p5/>.

⁷ The digital images of the 1496 incunabulum are reproduced courtesy of the Biblioteca del Senato della Repubblica "Giovanni Spadolini".

A central aspect of the methodology involves creating alternative access paths to the text, as a complement to linear reading, based on spatial and temporal dimensions. Starting from the lists of places and events encoded in the XML-TEI file, the edition offers interactive maps of the city and its territory, as well as a calendar of festivities, which allow users to explore the statutes starting from urban and territorial geography and the festive cycle.⁸ These visualisations directly connect space and time to the statutory rubrics, transforming these dimensions into keys for accessing the normative text.

Figure 1. Structural overview of the statutes of Ascoli.

In addition to spatial and temporal paths, the edition includes a list of people mentioned in the statutes, compiled from the codification of names occurring in the text, and a thematic taxonomy composed of 20 categories, applied to a selection of rubrics. The thematic categories organise the corpus according to recurring conceptual domains of the institutional, social, and economic life of the Ascoli community (see Figure 2). Since not all statutory provisions lend themselves to an unambiguous classification, thematic categorisation was applied only to a selection of rubrics (203, approximately 40% of the 513 rubrics). For each categorised rubric, a summary of the normative content was also included as a mediation tool for non-specialist audiences. These summaries accompany the original text and facilitate comprehension where the legal language is particularly complex.

The digital encoding also accounts for the internal cross-referential nature of the statutory text, as certain rubrics explicitly refer to other rubrics within the corpus as normative precedents or points of clarification. A total of 27 internal references were identified and encoded as hyperlinks, enabling direct navigation between related rubrics and supporting a non-linear mode of consultation that reflects the interconnected structure of the statutes.

In line with an approach oriented towards public history and user participation, the digital edition also integrates mechanisms for audience engagement. In fact, several sections of the website feature a *call-to-action* inviting users to report any transcription errors or to contribute information regarding people and places mentioned in the statutes, particularly in cases where toponyms or other terms may reflect vernacular forms that still coexist in local dialect usage. This feedback channel is conceived as a tool for

⁸ The construction of the maps is based on a process of historical and topographical reconstruction derived from the indications contained in the statutes, integrated with later cadastral and cartographic sources (see the project *Catasto 1381 Ascoli*, available at: <https://catasto1381ascoli.archiviostatatoap.it/>). The festive calendar was reconstructed with reference to Cappelli (1998: 60, 137–189).

dialogue with the user community and as a possible support for the progressive improvement and enrichment of the edition.

Alongside its scholarly and user-oriented aims, the project placed emphasis on the technical implementation of the digital edition, guided by a commitment to long-term sustainability. The digital edition of the statutes of Ascoli was developed using a fully static architecture. The website is published via GitHub Pages and is based exclusively on static files (HTML, CSS, JavaScript, and XML), ensuring autonomous operation and minimal maintenance over time. This implementation choice was guided by concerns for sustainability and persistence, aiming to reduce risks and costs related to infrastructure maintenance and to ensure the durability and continued accessibility of the edition.

Figure 2. Visualisation of the Categories access path. The selected category Family displays the list of rubrics associated with this domain, allowing users to explore the corpus through a thematic perspective.

Together, these methodological choices enable a shift from linear reading to multi-path exploration, in which space, time, people, and themes act as orienting devices. XML-TEI encoding thus constitutes the infrastructure that connects the normative text to its multiple dimensions of meaning, supporting a model of digital edition that is attentive to the complexity of the source and to the needs of accessibility and comprehension of different audiences.

4. NAMED ENTITY RECOGNITION

The named entity annotation produced during the encoding process represents one of the most philologically demanding components of the edition. The 222 unique entities manually identified and encoded across the corpus (28 individuals, 126 places, and 68 festivities or events) were annotated according to a set of principles grounded in the specific documentary conventions of the source. For places, the annotated span consistently encompasses the full nominal group as it appears in the statutory text, including the place-denoting noun where present: *castello de Appignano*, *ecclesia de Sancta Maria majore*, *palazzo del Popolo* are tagged in their entirety rather than reduced to the bare toponym. For individuals, spans include the full name as given, with patronymic or place of origin where the text provides them: *Muctio de Johanni de Bernardo*, *Joanni da Theramo*. For festivities, the full liturgical formula is retained: *festas de sancto Emidio*, *venardi sancto*. These conventions reflect the structure of the source itself, in which names rarely appear in isolation but are embedded in the syntactic and formulaic patterns of communal statutory language.

To assess the extent to which such annotation could be replicated automatically, we conducted an experiment using two large language models: LLaMA 3.3 70B and Qwen 2.5 72B.⁹ Both models were prompted with a structured definition of the three entity categories (PER for person, LOC for location, and FES for festivity) and instructed to return entity spans. The manual annotations served as the gold

⁹ Model resources: LLaMA 3.3 70B Instruct (<https://huggingface.co/meta-llama/Llama-3.3-70B-Instruct>) and Qwen 2.5 72B Instruct (<https://huggingface.co/Qwen/Qwen2.5-72B-Instruct>). The codebase, prompts, and experimental results are available at <https://github.com/statutiascoli/ner>. Computations were performed using HPC resources provided by the Erlangen National High Performance Computing Center (NHR@FAU) at Friedrich-Alexander Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg (FAU), within the framework of the BayernKI initiative, funded by the Bavarian state government.

standard. Evaluation was performed under two criteria: exact match, requiring both the correct category and the precise character span, and overlap match, defined here as intersection over union (IoU) ≥ 0.5 , which accepted predictions with the correct category whose span overlapped at least half of the gold span (Table 1).

Under exact matching, both models achieved modest overall F1 scores. LLaMA reached 0.277 and Qwen reached 0.348. PER yielded the strongest results, with F1 values of 0.444 and 0.526 respectively. LOC and FES proved more challenging, with F1 values ranging from 0.258 to 0.370. The discrepancy between exact and overlap scores highlights a systematic pattern. Under overlap matching, overall F1 rises dramatically to 0.635 for LLaMA and 0.655 for Qwen. The largest gains are in LOC (+0.33 and +0.30) and FES (+0.49 and +0.36). This pattern reveals that the predominant error mode is not a failure to identify the correct referent, but a difference in span delimitation. Models identify the correct text region but struggle to align with editorial span boundaries, tending to omit the place-denoting noun (e.g., reducing *castello de Appignano* to *Appignano*) or the liturgical designation (e.g., reducing *festa de sancto Emidio* to *sancto Emidio*). PER shows a smaller gap overall, as personal name spans tend to be syntactically more compact in this corpus.

Exact match	LLaMA 3.3 70B			Qwen 2.5 72B		
	P	R	F1	P	R	F1
PER	0.341	0.636	0.444	0.429	0.682	0.526
LOC	0.293	0.230	0.258	0.315	0.334	0.324
FES	0.323	0.244	0.278	0.352	0.389	0.370
Overall	0.306	0.253	0.277	0.333	0.365	0.348
Overlap (IoU \geq 0.5)	P	R	F1	P	R	F1
PER	0.439	0.818	0.571	0.514	0.818	0.632
LOC	0.672	0.528	0.591	0.607	0.644	0.625
FES	0.889	0.672	0.765	0.697	0.771	0.732
Overall	0.702	0.580	0.635	0.625	0.687	0.655

Table 1. Precision (P), recall (R), and F1 for LLaMA 3.3 70B and Qwen 2.5 72B on named entity recognition, evaluated with exact and overlap (IoU \geq 0.5) matching.

These results speak to a broader characteristic of the source. The vernacular of the 1496 printed statutes of Ascoli is a hybrid register that combines medieval legal formulae with local dialectal features. This linguistic specificity poses a particular challenge for models trained predominantly on modern text (Esposito, 2025: 15-16). The vernacular character of the statutes thus lends itself to further linguistic investigation, and the experiment reported represents a first step in that direction, establishing a baseline against which future approaches can be meaningfully compared.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The digital edition of the statutes of Ascoli aims to contribute to the debate on scholarly digital editions of medieval normative sources, addressing in an integrated manner the issues of scholarly rigour, accessibility, and long-term sustainability. Starting from a transcription encoded in XML-TEI, the project highlights the structural complexity of the text and enables differentiated modes of exploration, grounded in spatial, temporal, and thematic dimensions, designed for specialist and non-specialist audiences. The adoption of a static architecture responds to the critical issues related to the durability of digital projects, proposing the edition as a resource for the study of the institutional history of the city and as a sustainable and replicable model for digital editions of medieval legal sources.

Finally, the named entity annotation that underpins the access paths also served as the basis for an experiment in automated recognition. The results confirm that large language models can identify entity-bearing regions in the text with reasonable accuracy, even in the absence of training data specific to this domain. At the same time, the gap between exact and overlap performance reveals that span delimitation is shaped by editorial conventions that are not easily recovered from a prompt description alone, and that the vernacular register of the source adds a further layer of difficulty. These findings point to productive directions for future work, combining NLP-based approaches with the crowdsourcing of local and dialectological knowledge from the community of Ascoli, with the aim of deepening the linguistic study of the corpus and supporting the development of a dedicated glossary.

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